

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium as Vanadium(IV)-citrate Complex

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A large number of photometric methods are reported in literature for the determination of vanadium. In view of limitations of these methods, we have developed a method of determination for vanadium with a view to overcome such problems.

Citrate is found to form a complex with vanadium(IV) which can be extracted from slightly acidic solutions with a tri-n-hexylamine solution in chloroform to give a purplish-blue extract. Under the proposed conditions of vanadium extraction, none of the analytical important elements was found to interfere. Accordingly, a highly selective method based on citrate complex of vanadium(IV) is presented here for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(V) can be reduced to vanadium(IV) by a number of reductants¹, but ascorbic acid has been found to be a suitable and convenient reductant as it rapidly reduces vanadium(V) to vanadium(IV). Vanadium(IV) thus produced is complexed with citrate solution giving a purplish-blue complex which is used for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium after extracting it with a tri-n-hexylamine solution.

The reagent blank shows a sharp absorption band at 375 nm but its absorbance decreases sharply on going toward longer wavelength and becomes negligibly small at 565 nm and beyond. The vanadium(V)-citrate complex exhibits an absorption band at 565 nm. Therefore, all absorbance studies were made at 565 nm.

Effect of varying experimental conditions: In the study of these parameters, unless varied, the aqueous phase (10 ml) containing 5 mg of vanadium, sodium citrate solution (1.5 ml) and ascorbic acid (200 mg), was extracted with tri-n-hexylamine solution in chloroform (10 ml) having equilibration

time of 1 min. The effect of citrate and ascorbic acid concentrations and of equilibration time on the absorbance of vanadium(IV)-citrate complex was studied (Table 1). The influence of pH was studied from 20 ml aqueous solution. Absorbance was found to be maximum in the pH range 1.6–3.2. However, after the addition of 200 mg of ascorbic acid or more, pH-adjustment is not required, thus making the method simpler and rapid.

Effect of extraction solvents: The vanadium(IV)-citrate complex is not extracted into benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl alcohol, n-butanol, ethyl acetate, amyl acetate and n-hexane. The complex was found to be unextractable in tribenzylamine but it gets extracted into tri-n-hexylamine, trioctylamine and tri-isooctylamine. Tri-n-hexylamine was chosen as the extractant as it gives the highest absorbance. The study of the variance of tri-n-hexylamine concentration in chloroform indicated that the absorbance increases upto 2% which remains unchanged till its concentration becomes 4%.

The optimum conditions for maximum absorbance of vanadium(IV)-citrate complex are: 200–500 mg of ascorbic acid, 1.2–1.8 ml of 2% (w/v) sodium citrate solution, 2–4% (v/v) tri-n-hexylamine solution and 10–40 min equilibration time.

Beer's law, stability and statistical parameters: Beer's law is valid in the concentration range 0.02–0.48 mg V/ml of the solvent phase. For 0.35 mg V/ml or more, the amount of citrate and ascorbic acid should be double of the requisite concentrations. A single extraction removes more than 96% of vanadium, however, second extraction is recommended for quantitative recovery. The complex is stable at least for 42 h. Eight samples, each containing 5 mg of vanadium were analysed. The relative standard deviation was found to be 2.3%.

Composition of the complex: The stoichiometry of the complex was investigated by Job's method of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT PARAMETERS ON THE ABSORBANCE OF VANADIUM(IV)-CITRATE COMPLEX

Citrate concn. (ml)	0.2	0.6	1.0	1.2–1.8	2.0	3.0
Absorbance	0.061	0.127	0.187	0.205	0.195	0.145
Ascorbic acid (mg)		50	100	200–500	800	
Absorbance		0.001	0.123	0.209	0.188	
Equilibration time (min)		1.0–4.0	5.0	7.0	10.0	
Absorbance		0.208	0.200	0.196	0.189	

Conditions: 0.5 mg V/ml of the aqueous phase; $\lambda_{\max}$ = 565 nm; single extraction with 10 ml of 2% (v/v) tri-n-octylamine solution.

continuous variations². The ratio of vanadium to citrate in the extracted species is 1 : 1. Similarly, by using the continuous variations method, ratio of vanadium to tri-n-hexylamine was found to be 1 : 2 and the ratio of citrate to tri-n-hexylamine as 1 : 2. The ratio of vanadium : citrate : tri-n-hexylamine in the extracted species is found to be 1 : 1 : 2.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of various anions and complexing agents on the extraction of vanadium(IV)-citrate complex was studied and their tolerance limits are: sulphate (200 mg), fluoride and acetate (10 mg each); nitrate, chloride, bromide and iodide (5 mg each); thiourea (500 mg) and tartrate (100 mg). Oxalate, phosphate and EDTA interfere seriously.

Of the 30 metal ions tested, only Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, Ti^{IV} and U^{VI} are found to give coloured extracts under the proposed conditions of vanadium extraction. The extraction of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} can be prevented by masking with tartrate (100 mg). The interference of Ti^{IV} can be avoided by fluoride (10 mg). Fe^{II} is not extracted, but with Fe^{III}, a coloured extract is obtained which can be prevented by passing carbon dioxide for 5 min through the aqueous solution and adding ascorbic acid (0.4 g). U^{VI} is tolerated only upto 0.5 mg. In higher amounts it forms golden coloured extract. Hydrolysable metal ions such as Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Sb^{III}, As^{III} and Sn^{II} give emulsion in higher concentrations on shaking with the tri-n-hexylamine solution, thus causing a decrease in their tolerance limits to 5 mg. Tl^I and Al^{III} lower the extraction of vanadium, however, the decrease in vanadium extraction in presence of these ions can be compensated by adding double the amount of optimum citrate concentration. The tolerance limits for different foreign ions are as follows (amount in parenthesis): Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Zn^{II} (30 mg each); Ce^{IV} (25 mg); Mn^{II}, Tl^I (20 mg each); Ni^{II}, W^{VI} (15 mg each); Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ag^I (10 mg each); Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Be^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Sb^{III}, As^{III}, Sn^{II}, Cr^{VI}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Mo^{VI} (5 mg each); Th^{IV}, Re^{VII} (2 mg each); Al^{III}, Ti^{IV} (1 mg each); 0.5 mg of U^{VI} do not interfere.

Applications: The proposed method for the determination of vanadium is one of the highly selective methods. The method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 10 min for a single determination. Beer's law range of the method is sufficiently large. The method can be compared favourably with the other known methods of vanadium determination based on the complexation either of vanadium(V) or vanadium(IV) as shown in Table 2. The method can be used in the analysis of natural and industrial products especially those containing vanadium in high proportions. Applicability of the method has been tested by the satisfactory analysis of high speed steel sample and some synthetic samples.

Experimental

A GS 5700 A spectrophotometer and a pH 5652 pH-meter were used.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE METHOD WITH OTHER METHODS

Sl. no.	Reagent	Extractant $\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	Beer's law/ (Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g V/cm}^2$)
1.	V(V), 3-N-salicyline amino- 4-hydroxybenzene sulphonic acid ^a	420	0-4.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (0.004)
2.	V(V), N-allyl-N'-(p benzoyl- glycine)thiourea ^b	Isoamyl alcohol 360 and 380	1-22 ppm (0.048)
3.	V(V), hydrogen peroxide ^c	— 450-460	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (0.18)
4.	V(IV), thiothenoyl- trifluoroacetone ^d	CCl ₄ -butanol (1:1) 450 nm	— (0.0014)
5.	V(IV), chromazol KS ^e	600 nm	0-40 $\mu\text{g/25 ml}$ —
6.	V(V), 3,5-dinitrocatechol and brilliant green ^f	630 nm	0.005-0.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ —
7.	Present method	THA-CHCl ₃ , 565 nm	0.02-0.48 mg/ml (1.98)

^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 4. ^cRef. 5. ^dRef. 6. ^eRef. 7. ^fRef. 8

A standard stock solution of vanadium (5 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from ammonium metavanadate which was standardised titrimetrically³. Lower concentrations (50 and/or 100 $\mu\text{g V/ml}$) were obtained by suitable dilutions. Solutions of other metal ions were prepared in distilled water or dilute HCl. A 2% (w/v) solution of sodium citrate was prepared in distilled water. Ascorbic acid was used as a reductant. Tri-n-hexylamine solution (2%, v/v) was made in chloroform.

Synthetic samples for testing the applicability of the method were prepared by mixing the solutions of other metal ions with known amounts of vanadium.

Procedure: To the solution containing 0.5-12.0 mg of vanadium, ascorbic acid (200 mg) was added with shaking, followed by the addition of sodium citrate solution (1.5 ml) and enough distilled water to make the total volume of aqueous phase to 10 ml. The complex was extracted for 1 min with tri-n-hexylamine solution (2 × 10 ml). The volume of the combined extract was made up to 25 ml with the solvent. The absorbance of purplish-blue complex was measured at 565 nm against the reagent blank.

The interference of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} was prevented by the adding tartrate and of Ti^{IV} by adding fluoride to the aqueous solution.

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